

Awareness and perception of nanomaterials in the management of dentin hypersensitivity and their periodontal applications among dental professionals

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ABSTRACT

Title: Awareness and Perceptions of Dental Professionals Regarding Nanomaterials in the Management of Dentin Hypersensitivity

Aim: To assess the awareness, clinical experiences, and perceptions of postgraduate dental students and general practitioners regarding the etiology, pathophysiology, and management of DH, with a focus on the role of nanomaterials.

Materials and Methods: A cross-sectional survey was conducted among 80 dental professionals using a 28-item questionnaire. The survey collected information on clinical encounters with Dentin hypersensitivity(dh), perceived causes, understanding of pathophysiology, and familiarity with conventional and nanomaterial-based management strategies. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze responses.

Results: Of the 80 respondents, 78.8% (n=63) reported encountering patients with DH associated with gingival recession. The frequency of cases was reported as “sometimes” by 61.2%, “often” by 23.8%, “rarely” by 11.2%, and “very frequently” by 3.8%. Tooth wear due to abrasion, erosion, or attrition was identified as the most common cause (53.8%), followed by gingival recession (18.8%), post-scaling/root planing (18.8%), and carious or defective restorations (7.5%). Regarding pathophysiology, the hydrodynamic theory was the most widely accepted explanation (58.8%), followed by the odontoblast receptor theory (28.8%) and direct innervation theory (6.3%). Awareness of nanomaterials such as nano-hydroxyapatite and calcium phosphate nanoparticles was moderate, with most respondents recognizing their role in occluding dentinal tubules and promoting remineralization.

Conclusion: Dental professionals encounter Dentin hypersensitivity frequently, particularly in association with gingival recession and tooth wear. While the hydrodynamic theory is well-recognized, misconceptions regarding other mechanisms persist. Awareness of nanomaterials

as a management option is growing but remains incomplete, highlighting the need for targeted educational interventions and evidence-based training to enhance clinical adoption.

Keywords: Dentin hypersensitivity, Gingival recession, Nanomaterials, Nano-hydroxyapatite, Dental education, Periodontology

INTRODUCTION

Periodontitis is a multifactorial, polymicrobial disease of the oral cavity characterized by progressive destruction of the tooth-supporting tissues. It is caused by multiple factors, such as pathogenic bacteria, genetic predisposition, and host immune response factors). Periodontitis is a chronic inflammatory disease of the periodontal tissues characterized by loss of connective tissue attachment and alveolar bone, which often leads to gingival recession and exposure of root surfaces. Periodontal attachment loss has been recognized as a risk factor for gingival recession, exposing the tooth cementum and dentin surfaces to the oral environment ^{1,2}.

Gingival recession, whether caused by periodontitis, traumatic brushing, or other etiologic factors, results in loss of the protective covering over the root surface (cementum), leading to exposure of dentin. This exposed dentin is more vulnerable to external stimuli because cementum is thin and easily worn away ³. Dentin hypersensitivity (DH) is a painful dental condition that arises when stimuli—thermal, tactile, osmotic, chemical act upon exposed dentin tubules, leading to sharp, short-lasting pain that cannot be explained by other dental pathology. The hydrodynamic theory remains the most accepted mechanistic explanation: fluid movement within open dentinal tubules, when stimulated, causes activation of mechano- and thermo-sensitive nerve fibers in the pulp, resulting in pain. Multiple factors contribute to DH in the context of periodontology. Besides exposure of dentin via recession, periodontal treatment procedures such as scaling and root planing may further remove smear layer and cementum, rendering dentinal tubules more patent and thereby increasing sensitivity ^{2,3,4}.

Additionally, periodontitis patients often have higher prevalence of DH, and attachment loss (or recession) often correlates with severity and incidence of DH. For example, in a study of chronic periodontitis patients in Chandigarh, 47.8% showed clinical DH and attachment loss was associated with hypersensitivity ⁵.

The presence of DH has considerable impact on quality of life—it can interfere with eating, drinking, tooth brushing, and general comfort—thereby possibly affecting oral hygiene

routines, which may in turn exacerbate periodontal inflammation and recession. Thus, DH is not merely a symptom but can function in a self-reinforcing cycle with periodontal disease and recession ⁶.

Conventional treatments for DH include home-care agents (desensitizing toothpastes with potassium salts, fluoride, or arginine), in-clinic agents (bonding agents, varnishes), physical coverings, or laser therapy. While these may provide relief, they have limitations in terms of durability, degree of tubule occlusion, resistance to acid/abrasion, and complete relief ^{2,3}.

Nanomaterials have emerged as promising adjuncts or alternatives in managing DH, due to their small size, high surface area, ability to deeper penetrate dentinal tubules, and potential for promoting remineralization. Nano-hydroxyapatite (n-HAP) is one of the most studied, both in vitro and clinically, showing good tubule occlusion, reduced sensitivity (air, tactile, evaporative stimuli), and comparable or better performance than many conventional agents ^{4,7}. Other nanomaterials, such as mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs), mesoporous calcium silicate nanoparticles, zinc-doped nanoparticles, and novel complex formulations (e.g., polyelectrolyte-calcium complexes) have also shown in vitro (and some in vivo) efficacy in occluding dentinal tubules, resisting acid/abrasion challenges, and in some cases releasing therapeutic agents like antimicrobials ⁸.

Accordingly, it is important to evaluate the awareness of dental professionals (or patients) regarding the application of nanomaterials in the treatment of dentin hypersensitivity and their potential role in periodontology. By highlighting shortcomings, this assessment can guide the development of educational strategies and support the adoption of innovative, evidence-based materials in everyday clinical practice.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Study Design

A cross-sectional survey using a self-administered online questionnaire (Google Forms) was conducted among postgraduate students and general practitioners to evaluate their awareness regarding the role of nanomaterials in managing dentin hypersensitivity (DH) and their broader applications in Periodontology.

Study Population

The study population consisted of postgraduate students and general practitioners. Participants were included if they were actively involved in clinical practice or training, ensuring that the respondents had adequate exposure to clinical scenarios relevant to the management of dentin hypersensitivity and the application of nanomaterials in periodontology. Postgraduates from non-clinical specialties were excluded to maintain the clinical relevance of the responses; however, students from the Department of Oral Medicine and Radiology were included, as their training involves significant exposure to patient assessment and treatment planning. This approach allowed for the collection of responses from individuals with practical experience in patient care, ensuring that the findings accurately reflect the awareness and perceptions of dental professionals directly engaged in clinical practice.

Questionnaire Design

A structured, self-administered questionnaire was developed after an extensive review of relevant literature to ensure content validity. The questionnaire was designed to cover three key domains: (1) assessment of awareness regarding dentin hypersensitivity and its etiology, (2) evaluation of knowledge concerning nanomaterials and their applications in dentistry, and (3) exploration of participants' perceptions and willingness to adopt nanotechnology in clinical practice. It comprised 28 multiple-choice questions aimed at assessing both factual knowledge and opinion-based responses.

Validation of the Questionnaire

To ensure clarity, relevance, and comprehensiveness, the questionnaire was reviewed and validated by three subject experts in Meenakshi Ammal dental college.

Data Collection & Analysis

The validated questionnaire was distributed electronically via Google Forms, with participants provided clear instructions prior to completion. Confidentiality and anonymity of all responses were strictly maintained. The collected data were compiled in Microsoft Excel, and inferential statistical analysis, including the Chi-square test, was performed to evaluate participants' awareness levels.

OBSERVATION AND RESULTS

Among 80 respondents, 78.8% (n=63) reported encountering patients with dentin hypersensitivity (DH) associated with gingival recession, while 21.2% (n=17) had not observed such cases. In terms of frequency, the majority (61.2%) encountered such cases “sometimes,” followed by 23.8% “often,” 11.2% “rarely,” and only 3.8% “very frequently” (**Figure 1a**). Tooth wear due to abrasion, erosion, or attrition was identified as the most common cause of DH (53.8%), followed by gingival recession (18.8%), post-scaling/root planing (18.8%), and carious or defective restorations (7.5%) (**Figure 1b**). Regarding pathophysiology, the hydrodynamic theory was the most widely accepted explanation (58.8%), followed by the odontoblast receptor theory (28.8%) and the direct innervation theory (6.3%) (**Figure 1c**).

(Figure 1a – 1c)

When asked about first-line treatment for gingival recession–associated DH, more than half (56.3%) recommended desensitizing toothpastes containing fluoride, potassium nitrate, or strontium salts, followed by topical varnishes/sealants (21.3%), lasers (12.5%), and restorative coverage (10%) (**Figure 2a**). Overall, desensitizing toothpastes were the most frequently used modality, while other options such as restorative coverage, periodontal surgery, lasers, and

varnishes were applied in selected cases (**Figure 2b**). Over-the-counter desensitizing toothpastes received a mean effectiveness score of 3.48 (± 1.02), reflecting moderate confidence

among practitioners (**Figure 2c**).

(Figure 2a-2c)

Awareness of advanced management options showed that 23.8% of respondents were familiar with dentin bonding agents, 23.8% with nanoparticle-based materials (such as nano-hydroxyapatite and bioactive glass), 16.3% with iontophoresis, and 8.8% with lasers (**Figure 3a**). Overall, 73.8% were aware of the use of nanoparticles in dentistry, and 61.3% specifically recognized their application in DH management. Among nanoparticles, nano-hydroxyapatite (26.3%) and calcium phosphate nanoparticles (13.8%) were most frequently identified, with the majority (50%) believing their mechanism of action involves remineralization of exposed dentin, while others attributed it to nerve desensitization (22.5%) or tubule occlusion (21.3%) (**Figure 3b–c**). In terms of clinical effectiveness, 45% felt nanoparticle-based agents provided

the same duration of relief as conventional agents, 23.8% believed they offered longer-lasting relief, while 17.5% reported a shorter effect (mean score 3.05 ± 1.12) (**Figure 3d**).

(Figure3a-3d)

In the context of periodontal applications, 67.5% were aware of nanomaterials, most commonly nano-hydroxyapatite and bioactive glass. Reported uses included guided tissue regeneration (GTR) membranes, bone grafts, implant coatings, drug delivery systems, and wound healing (**Figure 4a**). More than half of the participants (51.3%) had observed or used nanoparticle-based products, with patient satisfaction rated as satisfied (40%), neutral (32.5%), very satisfied (15%), dissatisfied (10%), and very dissatisfied (2.5%) (**Figure 4b**). Clinical outcomes were favorable, with 57.5% reporting good outcomes, 25% moderate, 11.3% excellent, and only 6.3% poor (**Figure 4c**).

(Figure 4a-4c)

Regarding periodontal applications of nanomaterials, the majority of respondents (37.5%) identified their use in the management of dentin hypersensitivity, followed by local drug delivery systems (36.3%), periodontal dressings and wound healing (31.3%), guided tissue regeneration membranes (27.5%), and implant surface coatings (27.5%), while 20% mentioned bone grafts and substitutes and 10% were unsure (**Figure 5a**). When asked about specific nanomaterials known for periodontal applications, nano-hydroxyapatite was most recognized (47.5%), followed by bioactive glass nanoparticles (35%), titanium dioxide nanoparticles (26.3%), silver nanoparticles (22.5%), polymeric nanoparticles (15%), and chitosan nanoparticles (13.8%) (**Figure 5b**). Participants attributed the regenerative potential of nanomaterials to multiple mechanisms, primarily improved surface bioactivity for tissue attachment (35%), antibacterial action in periodontal pockets (33.8%), enhanced drug delivery with sustained release (31.3%), and promotion of osteoblast activity and bone formation (27.5%) (**Figure 5c**). Among those who had used nanomaterial-based products, 33.3% reported “no specific product” identified, while smaller proportions (16.7% each) mentioned various materials, including general or unspecified applications.

(Figure5a -5c)

Barriers to the adoption of nanoparticles included lack of awareness among practitioners (38.8%), high cost (21.3%), limited clinical evidence (20%), and poor market availability (16.3%) (**Figure 6a**). Although the likelihood of nanoparticles replacing conventional agents was rated moderately (mean 2.86), 63.8% recommended including them in standard protocols, and 71.3% expressed interest in attending workshops on nanotechnology (**Figure 6b**). Overall, nanotechnology was considered a promising adjunct in periodontal and DH management, with its potential benefits for periodontal regeneration rated at 3.28, while the perceived impact of DH on patients' quality of life received a mean score of 3.16 (**Figure 6c**).

(Figure 6a- 6c)

The present study revealed that a majority of respondents (approximately 75%) reported encountering patients with dentin hypersensitivity associated with gingival recession, with most indicating that such cases were seen occasionally, while a smaller proportion reported encountering them rarely. Tooth wear, including abrasion, erosion, and attrition, emerged as the most commonly identified cause of dentin hypersensitivity, followed by gingival recession. In terms of the underlying mechanism, the odontoblast receptor theory was most frequently selected, followed by the hydrodynamic theory. Regarding treatment practices, desensitizing toothpastes containing fluoride or potassium nitrate were cited as the first-line intervention, with additional modalities including varnishes, sealants, and restorative coverage frequently employed. Awareness of nanomaterials in dentistry was high among participants, with many specifically acknowledging their application in managing dentin hypersensitivity. Nano-

hydroxyapatite and silver nanoparticles were the most recognized agents, and a significant proportion of respondents believed that nanoparticle-based products provide superior and longer-lasting relief compared to conventional treatments. Clinically, those who had utilized nanoparticle-based products reported that patients were generally satisfied to very satisfied, and outcomes were rated as good to excellent; however, limitations such as high cost, limited clinical evidence, and lack of practitioner familiarity were noted. Looking to the future, many participants expressed the belief that nanoparticles could eventually replace conventional agents, advocated for their inclusion in standard treatment protocols, and showed interest in attending workshops or training sessions on nanotechnology. Additionally, the majority agreed that nanotechnology has the potential to enhance periodontal regeneration outcomes. Finally, respondents strongly concurred that dentin hypersensitivity significantly impacts patients' quality of life, underscoring the clinical importance of effective management strategies.

DISCUSSION

The present cross-sectional study assessed the awareness and perceptions of postgraduate dental students and general practitioners regarding the use of nanomaterials in the management of dentin hypersensitivity (DH) and their broader applications in periodontology. The findings of this study provide a contemporary overview of how well dental professionals understand nanotechnology-based interventions, revealing both encouraging awareness levels and persisting knowledge gaps that influence clinical adoption.

The results demonstrated that the majority of respondents frequently encountered patients presenting with dentin hypersensitivity, particularly in association with gingival recession. This observation aligns with several previous studies which have consistently identified gingival recession as one of the predominant etiological factors predisposing to DH due to dentinal exposure and open tubules facilitating fluid movement^{9,10,11}. Similarly, tooth wear caused by abrasion, erosion, or attrition was also recognized by over half of the participants as a major causative factor, emphasizing the multifactorial aetiology of DH reported in earlier literature^{12,13}. These findings reaffirm the clinical relevance of DH in daily practice and the need for evidence-based management strategies.

Regarding the pain mechanism, the hydrodynamic theory proposed by Brännström remains the most widely acknowledged explanation among respondents, which is consistent with the prevailing scientific consensus¹⁴. Nonetheless, a notable proportion of participants still supported the odontoblast receptor theory, suggesting that traditional concepts continue to

persist within dental education and that greater emphasis should be placed on reinforcing evidence-based physiological understanding in postgraduate training. This persistence of outdated theoretical models is a recurring concern noted in educational research within dental curricula ¹⁵.

When treatment preferences were analysed, desensitizing toothpastes containing potassium nitrate, fluoride, or strontium salts emerged as the first-line management approach among most respondents, consistent with the recommendations of international guidelines and earlier reports by the Canadian Advisory Board on Dentin Hypersensitivity ¹². Although these agents provide symptomatic relief, their effects are often temporary and vary depending on patient compliance, formulation, and application frequency ^{13,16}. Such limitations highlight the need for novel treatment modalities that offer more durable and biologically integrated results.

Within this context, nanomaterials have emerged as a promising class of agents capable of offering enhanced desensitization through dentinal tubule occlusion and biomimetic remineralization. In the present study, nearly three-fourths of the participants reported awareness of nanomaterials in dentistry, with more than half recognizing their specific role in the management of DH. This increasing awareness reflects the growing exposure of dental professionals to nanotechnology through both academic and commercial channels. Among these materials, nano-hydroxyapatite (n-HAP) was the most frequently identified agent, followed by calcium phosphate nanoparticles and bioactive glass. These findings align with numerous experimental and clinical studies that have demonstrated the effectiveness of n-HAP in occluding dentinal tubules, promoting remineralization, and providing long-lasting relief from hypersensitivity ^{17,18,19}. Nevertheless, only about half of the respondents correctly identified remineralization as the primary mechanism of action, while others incorrectly attributed efficacy to neural desensitization, revealing an incomplete understanding of the molecular and structural mechanisms governing these agents.

An interesting observation from this study was that a considerable proportion of participants believed nanomaterial-based desensitizing agents provided prolonged relief compared to conventional formulations. This perception corresponds with findings from clinical trials reporting sustained benefits of n-HAP and other nanomaterials over traditional fluorides ^{20,21}. However, conflicting results also exist, with certain studies noting similar short-term outcomes, emphasizing the need for further longitudinal clinical trials to establish robust evidence for long-term efficacy and patient-centered benefits ²².

Awareness of nanomaterials extended beyond desensitization into periodontology, where approximately two-thirds of the respondents recognized their potential applications in guided tissue regeneration (GTR), bone grafting, implant coatings, and wound healing. This awareness mirrors the growing body of research demonstrating that nanostructured materials can enhance cellular adhesion, osteoblast differentiation, angiogenesis, and overall tissue regeneration²³. Nano-hydroxyapatite and bioactive glass, in particular, have been shown to promote bone regeneration and periodontal attachment gain in both in vitro and in vivo studies, making them integral components in regenerative periodontal therapy²⁴. However, familiarity with emerging nanomaterials such as titanium dioxide, chitosan, and silver nanoparticles remained comparatively low among respondents, indicating limited curricular exposure and slower clinical translation.

While most practitioners reported satisfactory outcomes when using nanomaterial-based products, key barriers such as cost, limited market availability, and insufficient clinical evidence were consistently identified. These constraints are not unique to dentistry but are echoed across other biomedical fields, where nanotechnology implementation faces challenges of production complexity, standardization, and regulatory approval²⁵. Nonetheless, the strong interest expressed by the majority of respondents in attending educational workshops and incorporating nanotechnology into treatment protocols suggests a readiness to adopt innovation when adequate evidence and training are provided.

From a clinical standpoint, improving the understanding and application of nanomaterials could profoundly enhance patient outcomes. Dentin hypersensitivity, though often perceived as a minor dental issue, significantly affects quality of life by impairing eating, drinking, and oral hygiene habits. Inadequate management may indirectly contribute to periodontal deterioration due to poor plaque control. Nanomaterials, with their biomimetic properties and regenerative potential, can therefore play a dual role in symptom relief and periodontal health restoration. The integration of such materials into standard clinical care could bridge the gap between symptom management and tissue regeneration, marking a paradigm shift in preventive and restorative dentistry²⁶.

Educationally, the persistence of misconceptions and partial understanding highlighted by this study emphasizes the importance of strengthening postgraduate and continuing dental education curricula. Structured modules on nanoscience, material characterization, and clinical application can foster evidence-based decision-making and encourage early adoption of advanced technologies. Moreover, collaboration between academia, industry, and regulatory

bodies is essential to ensure that the translation of nanotechnology from research to routine practice is both ethical and effective.

Despite its valuable insights, the study has inherent limitations, including reliance on self-reported data and a geographically limited sample size, which may restrict generalizability. Future investigations should incorporate larger, more diverse samples and qualitative methodologies such as focus group interviews to better capture the perceptions and practical challenges faced by dental professionals in adopting nanotechnology.

CONCLUSION

The results of this study demonstrate a commendable level of awareness among dental practitioners regarding nanomaterials, particularly nano-hydroxyapatite and bioactive glass, in the management of dentin hypersensitivity and periodontal regeneration. Nevertheless, significant gaps in conceptual understanding, cost-related barriers, and limited clinical exposure continue to hinder widespread adoption. The positive attitude toward further training and inclusion of nanotechnology in clinical protocols highlights an encouraging trend toward modernization in dental education and practice. Strengthening research collaboration, expanding clinical trials, and integrating nanotechnology-based training modules are therefore pivotal steps toward achieving meaningful clinical translation and improved patient outcomes in the years to come

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